

Deliverable D8.3

Dissemination and Communication Report

WP 8

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Project Summary

The objective of smashHit is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a Framework for processing of data owner consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. The vision of smashHit is to overcome obstacles in the rapidly growing Data Economy which is characterized by heterogeneous technical designs and proprietary implementations, locking business opportunities due to the inconsistent consent and legal rules among different data-sharing platforms actors and operators. The Framework will provide methods and tools, such as Smart Data Dispatcher, to assure common consent over data shared using semantic models of consent and legal rules. The new tools include traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data owners, data providers, service providers and users. These tools are specifically critical for enormous volumes on data streaming from the usage of mass products with cyber physical features (e.g. vehicles). These data streams offer new opportunities to build innovative services, but their combination with other personal and industrial data is subject to complex ownership and consent aspects, as the data streaming from these products belong to persons or organizations who are owners or users of the products. The project will be based on the solutions developed or under development in previous and current projects (AutoMat, Cross-CPP, CAMPANEO, DALICC etc.). smashHit is driven by two industrial Business Cases involving several existing industrial and personal data platforms owned by the leading data providers in three diverse sectors (automotive industry, insurance, smart city), and will provide three demonstrators of various applications of the developed solutions.

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Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Document Summary

This deliverable reports on the outcomes of the first 18 months of the project for dissemination, communication and community building (period: January 2020-June 2021). It shows the methodology followed, the instruments and mechanisms used to raise the project awareness, the collaboration policy with other projects and related stakeholders and interested groups. It reports on the KPIs for assessing the progress and impact in the due formal reports. List of events, conferences, interest groups, open source communities, online press, journals, social networks, etc. where the project have taken part at is included.

Abbreviations

App	Software Application	i.e.	id est = that is to say
BDVA	Big Data Value Association	IoT	Internet of Things
BC	Business Case	IP	Intellectual Property
CPP	Cyber Physical Products	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
D	Deliverable	KPI	Key Performance Indicator
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan	M	Month
DoW	Description of Work	OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
EC	European Commission	PR	Public Relations
e.g.	Exempli gratia = for example	RTD	Research and Technological Development
EU	European Union	SME	Small and Medium Sized Enterprise
FP7	Framework Programme 7	T	Task
GA	Grant Agreement	WP	Work Package
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation		
ICT	Information and Communication Technology		

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1 Introduction

Deliverable D8.3 provides the dissemination and communication report for the first half of the smashHit Horizon 2020 EU project. smashHit recognises that awareness needs to be raised and suggests to do that by providing meaningful information in informative and engaging ways. Collaboration and communication are vital for achieving a good dissemination outcome. An appropriate dissemination strategy has been presented in detail in D8.1 “Dissemination and Communication Plan” (M3) [1], and this deliverable is basing on it, and is, de-facto its updated version, and is describing the implementation of this plan up to now.

In order to clearly understand the difference between Dissemination and Communication, which will be discussed later in this deliverable, the following comparison between the two is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Definitions of Communication and Dissemination

	Definition	Objective	Focus	Target
Communication	“brings attention of multiple audiences about your research (in a way that can be understood by non-specialists) and addresses the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding” ¹	Inform different audiences about the smashHit project and its purpose.	Raise awareness.	Audiences from various backgrounds and stakeholders.
Dissemination	“sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policy makers” ²	To contribute to the process of science. ²	Make results publicly available to others.	Industry, data owners, research groups, scientific community, policy makers, students, innovators.

1.1 Purpose

The detailed objectives of the project dissemination and communication activity, as described in the smashHit project are:

- To widely disseminate and communicate the project concept, developments and findings to identified stakeholders using effective communication means and strategies.
- By using existing communities related to the project interact with them to disseminate project results, get their feedback and integrating our results in them when possible.
- To create and publish scientific contributions valuable for the related research community.
- To collaborate with other European projects or interest groups in the relevant topics.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

- To participate in appropriate European and worldwide events (workshops, seminars, conferences, etc.) targeted at project topics with the ultimate goal to showcase the project results and subsequently to prepare the way for a successful business development of the project outcomes.
- Analyse the standards applicable for the project and which ones could be followed and contributed by the project.

1.2 Relation to other Projects

This project welcomes collaboration with other projects such as CampaNeo in order to develop innovative solutions, which would contribute to solving the ICT-13-2018-2019: Supporting the emergence of data markets and the data economy challenge. Selected projects related to smashHit are stated in Table 2.

Table 2: Related Projects

Project	Description	Website
CampaNeo	An open platform on which private and public institutions can create campaigns, collect and analyse vehicle data in real time.	https://projekte.ffg.at/projekt/3314668
SPECIAL	“SPECIAL allows citizens and organisations to share more data, while guaranteeing compliance with data protection, thus enabling both trust and the creation of valuable new insights from shared data.”	https://www.specialprivacy.eu
DALICC	Software that supports the automated clearance of rights thus supporting the legally secure and time-efficient reutilization of third-party data sources.	https://dalicc.net
enviroCar	An open citizen platform aimed at traffic and environment monitoring.	https://envirocar.org
AutoMat	“To establish a novel and open ecosystem in the form of a cross-border Vehicle Big Data Marketplace that leverages currently unused information gathered from a large amount of vehicles from various brands.”	https://automat-project.eu
MyData	“To empower individuals by improving their right to self-determination regarding their personal data.”	https://mydata.org
Cross-CPP	Creating access to sensor data from various industrial sectors to enable new dimension of innovative business ideas.	www.cross-cpp.eu

Project	Description	Website
i3-MARKET	Intelligent, Interoperable, Integrative and deployable open source MARKET place with trusted and secure software tools for incentivising the industry data economy.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871754
TRUSTS	Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space aims to develop a data-sharing platform for secure, trustworthy, and GDPR-compliant data exchanges.	https://www.trusts-data.eu
DataVaults	Persistent Personal Data Vaults Empowering a Secure and Privacy Preserving Data Storage, Analysis, Sharing and Monetisation Platform.	https://www.datavaults.eu

As discussed in the technical deliverables of the smashHit project, smashHit already has been synergetic with the development of other projects. For example, in some cases (e.g. CampaNeo, Cross-CPP) direct technology adoption and further development has already taken place, and in many further cases such development are in progress.

1.3 Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows.

- **Section 1** provides an introduction to the deliverable.
- **Section 2** presents the dissemination and communication strategy that is followed and provides a description of the main goals, focus, channels and audience of the smashHit project.
- Further activities, which help the dissemination, are specified in **Section 3**.
- **Section 4** describes in detail the planned success metrics and their achievement.
- Conclusion of the Dissemination and Communication Report can be found in **Section 5**.

2 The Dissemination and Communication Strategy

In this section, we outline the smashHit's dissemination and communication strategy, i.e. its set up and activities to be performed.

2.1 smashHit Strategy

The building blocks and the organisation of the smashHit communication and dissemination strategy are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Building Blocks for Dissemination and Communication

The strategy is divided in 3 main phases, which are described as follows:

- **Discovery (M1-M3):** is the kick-off phase where T8.1 and T8.2 in cooperation with T8.3 and T8.4, as well with the rest of the consortium define the overall building blocks under the communication and dissemination strategy phases that the project plans to follow up. It collects the initial insights about channels, target audiences, website, logo, social networks, newsletters, communication material, events and conferences, KPIs, reporting plans, among other key topics, which encompass this task.
- **Launch & Engage (M6-M12-M18):** after the initial set-up, it is expected that the project advances in developing research content and defines clear R&D&I topics where the dissemination actions might start. In addition, the experience and success metrics collected within Business Cases (BCs), Scenarios and Components specification would allow to create relevant content about the results and advances obtained to be communicated through the different channels and target audiences. This would lead to the generation of valuable material about smashHit value proposition, benefits, advantages that may be incorporated into the messages and communication created to external audiences.
- **Boost Involvement (M18-M36):** given the timeframe of this phase when early prototypes are ready and final prototypes are planned in the following 12 months, smashHit aims to open-up their networks incorporating feedback and continuous interaction exchange from external end-users and stakeholders. This engagement could evolve into the appearance of business development joint-actions for the smashHit Framework or for the Business Cases replication and extension. It is also the phase where the project would focus on sharing the Lessons Learned and Best Practices in secure and privacy-preserving data-sharing frameworks to the public.

2.2 Overall Set Up

Within this chapter the focus of our dissemination & communication strategy, the communication channels as well as the main target audiences will be identified.

GOALS: The main goal of smashHit is to ensure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a framework for processing of data owner consent, legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms.

CORE MESSAGE: The objective of smashHit is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a Framework for processing of data owner consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. The vision of smashHit is to overcome obstacles in the rapidly growing Data Economy, which is characterized by heterogeneous technical designs and proprietary implementations, locking business opportunities due to the inconsistent consent and legal rules among different data-sharing platforms actors and operators.

The smashHit program will deliver a framework and best practice for traceable data sharing and contracting with consumer consent for scenarios such as advanced smart city solutions or connected car insurance programs. In the same way, smashHit addresses the needs of businesses and consumers for the development of smart mobility solutions in a smart city context with sharing of personal data and traffic information. Unlike other initiatives, smashHit is formed by a consortium of nine organisations drawn from academia, analytics, data security and private enterprise working collaboratively to deliver the benefits of car connectivity to the consumer mass-market.

FOCUS: Scientific publications, communication and dissemination to broader audience and relevant stakeholders, particularly in relation to promoting a more general level innovation action, EU data economy, innovating new services, etc.

We intend spending some time on stakeholder mapping, to identify the critical groups that can contribute the most to the program's success. We have included an example of this below (Figure 2) where the stakeholders are ranked by interest (how interested are they in our program) and power/influence (how much authority or influence they have in our program).

Figure 2: Stakeholder Mapping

These are significant cross-country groups and within the time allocated to the project for communication, we could be at risk of spreading ourselves thinly. The purpose of this exercise is to identify which stakeholders need specific plans, and the priority of communication planning. We believe that the major groups are the EU, consumers, smart cities, insurers and car OEM's that require individual plans to be created. Journalists, regulators and trade associations would be managed as the program develops.

EXPLOITATION: The project's results that will be exploitable after the end of the project can be also disseminated with the channels developed in the project. According to the EU contract, the smashHit website will be maintained for after the project's end, as typically requested. However, exploitation related issues will be handled in the scope of Task 8.3 / 8.4 and deliverables D8.2, D8.5 & D8.6.

CHANNELS: Our channels include social media, press, web presence, newspapers and articles in journals, conferences and workshops, presentations, organizing or participating in events. Channels to be confirmed on completion of stakeholder mapping exercise (main audience). We anticipate a focus on trade and technical press, consumer press and conference attendance.

2.3 Main Audience and Stakeholders for Dissemination and Communication

As specified in the project proposal, the consortium has already envisioned key groups that will be targeted. The dissemination will address the following stakeholders with according activities:

- **Industry**
With this project we aim to address industries such as in the sectors of Technology, Insurance, Vehicle Manufacturing (Volkswagen³, Nissan⁴, Ford⁵), Transport, Big Data (Sciencesoft⁶, Hdata Systems⁷, Altoros⁸, Andersen⁹, Thirdeye Data¹⁰), Experienced users and everyday users.
REASON: To further publicise and contribute to our good practice recommendation and act as mentors.
ACTIVITIES: Newsletters, briefings, website, social media, exhibitions.
- **Policy makers**
Organizations that specialize in privacy, security and policies (IAPP¹¹, White & Case¹², Dentons¹³, Huntonak¹⁴, Bird&Bird¹⁵, EDPB¹⁶).
REASON: To co-create and use our evidence-based policy recommendations.
ACTIVITIES: Workshops, conferences, demonstrations, briefings, newsletters, website, social media, exhibitions.

³ <https://www.volkswagenag.com>

⁴ <https://www.nissan.at>

⁵ <https://www.ford.com>

⁶ <https://www.scnsoft.com>

⁷ <https://www.hdatasystems.com>

⁸ <https://www.althoros.com>

⁹ <https://andersenlab.com>

¹⁰ <https://thirdeyedata.io>

¹¹ <https://iapp.org>

¹² <https://www.whitecase.com/law/practices/data-privacy-cybersecurity>

¹³ <https://www.dentons.com/en/find-your-dentons-team/practices/privacy-and-security>

¹⁴ <https://www.huntonak.com/en/practices/privacy-and-cybersecurity/>

¹⁵ <https://www.twobirds.com>

¹⁶ https://edpb.europa.eu/edpb_en

- **Smart Cities**
Companies that focus on building smart cities that harness the power of technology to increase operational efficiency (Cisco¹⁷, Schneider Electric¹⁸, Siemens¹⁹, Oracle²⁰, FVH²¹).
REASON: To co-create and use our evidence-based policy recommendations.
ACTIVITIES: Workshops, conferences, demonstrations, briefings, newsletters, website, social media, exhibitions.
- **Students**
Bachelor, Master and PhD student who are interested in innovation, technology, machine learning, mobility/transport, Big Data and security.
REASON: To use our training materials and good practise recommendations and act as mentors.
ACTIVITIES: Online and offline courses, course materials, briefings, scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions.
- **Innovators**
People interested in technology, science, transport who want to be active.
REASON: To use our training materials and good practise recommendations and act as mentors.
ACTIVITIES: Briefings, scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions.
- **Related Projects**
Collaboration with projects that received funding in the same call as smashHit: such as **I3-MAR-KET**⁷², TRUSTS, DataVaults²², and a number of others.
REASON: To use our training materials and good practise recommendations and act as mentors.
ACTIVITIES: Briefings, scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops.
- **smashHit would build on the outcomes of and collaborate with the projects such as** CampaNeo, enviroCar [2], MobGeoSen [3], DALICC²³ [4].
REASON: To contribute and provide further publicity for our outputs.
ACTIVITIES: Briefings, scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions.
- **Scientific Community**
Research groups that focus on Data Analytics (Smart Data Analytics²⁴, Data Science and Evolution²⁵), Semantic Technology (STLab²⁶), Data Visualization (Stanford Visualization Group²⁷), Traceability, Security and Privacy (Center for Information Technology Policy (CITP)²⁸, SecUnity²⁹), Machine

¹⁷ <https://www.cisco.com>

¹⁸ <https://www.se.com/us/en/>

¹⁹ <https://new.siemens.com/global/en.html>

²⁰ <https://www.oracle.com/index.html>

²¹ <https://forumvirium.fi/en/projects/>

²² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871755>

²³ <https://www.dalicc.net>

²⁴ <http://sda.cs.uni-bonn.de>

²⁵ <https://www.helsinki.fi/en/researchgroups/data-science-and-evolution>

²⁶ <https://www.istc.cnr.it/en/group/stlab?page=2>

²⁷ <http://vis.stanford.edu>

²⁸ <https://citp.princeton.edu>

²⁹ <https://it-security-map.eu>

Learning (AMLab³⁰), Artificial Intelligence (The Alan Turing Institute³¹, IBM Research³²), Database Systems (Dresden Database System Group³³). More research groups could be found on the CLAIRE Research Network³⁴. smashHit will also aim at research conference attendees and readers of scientific journals.

REASON: To continue our good practice recommendations, conduct research in the identified gaps and develop student's skills.

ACTIVITIES: Scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions.

- **Start Ups**

smashHit would address Start-Ups in Technology (UiPath³⁵, Improbable³⁶, SIGFOX³⁷), Transport (AUTO1 Group³⁸, Glovo³⁹) and Business (Atom Bank⁴⁰, Monzo⁴¹).

REASON: To further publicise and contribute to our good practice recommendation and act as mentors.

ACTIVITIES: Scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters, exhibitions. **Standardisation Bodies**

Opportunity to collaborate towards extending existing standards and developing new specifications that enable an open ecosystem of components for developing IoT focused applications and services that address user data consent/control requirements, for example in ISO⁴² and BSI⁴³. Possible collaboration with standardization bodies such as OMG⁴⁴ and W3C⁴⁵.

REASON: To further publicise and contribute to our good practice recommendation and act as mentors, to collaborate and help extend existing standards.

ACTIVITIES: Scientific publications, conferences, demonstrations, workshops, newsletters.

In conclusion, we aim at diverse audiences to make sure that the project could be recognized by as many people as possible. Different groups of people would require a different dissemination approach, which we have envisioned and planned ahead. The dissemination activities are performed by all project partners, but they differ according to what the partners specialize in. Industrial partners approach relevant industry sectors as well as their distributors and client networks, while the academic and research partners aim at disseminating the project to the research community across Europe. Feedback from all stakeholders is valuable for the project's activities thus we will try to engage more with the audiences.

³⁰ <https://mlplatform.nl/researchgroups/machine-learning-group-university-of-amsterdam/>

³¹ <https://www.turing.ac.uk>

³² <https://www.research.ibm.com>

³³ <https://www.db.inf.tu-dresden.de>

³⁴ <https://claire-ai.org/network/>

³⁵ <http://uipath.com>

³⁶ <http://improbable.io/>

³⁷ <http://www.sigfox.com>

³⁸ <https://www.auto1-group.com/>

³⁹ <https://glovoapp.com/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.atombank.co.uk/>

⁴¹ <https://monzo.com>

⁴² <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

⁴³ <https://shop.bsigroup.com>

⁴⁴ <https://www.omg.org>

⁴⁵ <https://www.w3.org>

2.4 Communication and Dissemination Channels and Activities

The Communication and Dissemination Channels and Activities have been chosen while having in mind different online and off-line scenarios. With them we aim to address the multiple target audiences identified to perform concrete actions and to widespread specific messages which enhance the awareness and knowledge sharing of the smashHit project concept and its progress during its lifetime.

As starting point, the description of the main channels selected for the project are in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3: Dissemination and Communication Channels (1)

Figure 4: Dissemination and Communication Channels (2)

CHANNELS: Our channels include social media, press, web presence, newspapers, articles in journals, conferences and workshops, presentations, organizing or participating in events.

Table 3 outlines the original plan to approach the dissemination activities during the smashHit project's duration. The plan was generally followed, though with a change that many events have been held online and not onsite, due to the pandemic. This development has in particular directed our dissemination and communication efforts in the online spaces vs. the offline spaces, and more efforts and resources were dedicated to the online digital objects production and online presence, and less to the offline dissemination (e.g. travel and printed materials).

Table 3: Activities

Communication Channel	When	What	How
Social media and website	M1-M36	Setting up the web and social media presence and keep them updated.	Developing the project's website, logo, flyer and poster templates and establishing a presence on social media channels namely <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Twitter, • LinkedIn, • Zenodo, • ResearchGate, • Spotify, • YouTube.
Scientific publications	M12-M36	Publications in journals and conferences.	Share innovations with the research community by publishing open access publications.
Events and conferences	M6-M36	Publicize the projects activities and results.	Participate in conferences and workshops to share results and discuss publications.
Press releases	M6-M36	Raise awareness about the smashHit project within different audiences.	Share results with the general public by targeting mainstream media, newspapers and newsletters.
Briefings and demonstrations	M24/M36	Publicize the project and encourage participation.	Publicize our good recommendation practise by realising briefing and commercial material to a wide range of stakeholders. Demonstrate the following Business Cases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services using integrated CPP and insurance data, • Services using integrated traffic, smart city and CPP data.
Marketing material	M3-M36	Non-scientific marketing material to acquaint the public with the project.	Prepare and share posters and flyers to users who do not have scientific background or do not read scientific publications on daily basis.
Blog posts	M6/M12/M18/M36	Release selected news to the stakeholders.	Create a network of interested stakeholders and share the latest news with them via a blog post (basis for a newsletter) every 6 months.

3 The Dissemination Activities and their Sustainability

The main objectives for the smashHit dissemination are to promote results, optimise exploitation, promote technology transfer and to support a continuous supply of new information. This is achieved with the help of various activities such as conference participation, collaborations and paper publications. An active online and offline presence would be established to support the dissemination and communication even further. Collaboration between all partners is essential for the progress of this project.

According to Article 28, Section 28.1 from the Grant Agreement, all beneficiaries are obliged to exploit their results by:

- (a) Using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- (b) Developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- (c) Creating and providing a service, or
- (d) Using them in standardisation activities.

Further, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium) (Article 29, Section 29.1 of the smashHit project agreement).

This chapter will present all dissemination activities, which are being undertaken, in separate sections accordingly.

3.1 Project Repository

The smashHit employs project repositories that can be accessed by all partners as well as wider stakeholder groups. Namely, the repositories open only to project partners (such as Nextcloud⁴⁶), the partners’ repositories (e.g. publication databases of individual partners), and the repositories open for everyone (such as the project website, Github⁴⁷, Gitlab⁴⁸, Bitbucket⁴⁹).

smashHit aims to publish the resulting papers from the focused workgroups in open access journals and conferences. The dissemination plan details the process for making scientific publications available online. smashHit uses Zenodo⁵⁰ as a joint repository, which is part of the OpenAIRE⁵¹ service by the EC. In addition to this, individual partners will also use repositories available at their respective institutions (e.g. archiving services, personal websites) to enhance the dissemination of the scientific publications.

AIM: To have an open access environment where smashHit partners could collaborate and share their progress.

3.2 Social Media and Professional Networks

The project partners have created and aim to maintain the web and social media presence throughout the whole project. Tables 4 and 5 present the social and professional channels that are currently set up and in use. A strategy for each social media platform is presented in Section 3.5.

AIM: To spread information about smashHit, its purpose, tasks and results thus raise awareness among the general public. Further, to target possible new stakeholders and collaborators.

Comparing to our original online dissemination plan (presented in D8.1 [1]), we have extended our reach to further platforms that facilitate distribution of audio and video content, namely, YouTube, Spotify and

⁴⁶ <https://nextcloud.com/>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com>

⁴⁸ <https://about.gitlab.com>

⁴⁹ <https://bitbucket.org>

⁵⁰ <http://www.zenodo.org>

⁵¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

iTunes, for sharing podcasts. Production and distribution of such podcasts partly compensates for less exposures in terms of talks and meetings at events, which was caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 4: Social Media Platforms

Social Media	Link
Twitter	https://twitter.com/SmashhitP
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/smashhit
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnKnDSPB6fmn6kzKo716baA
Spotify	https://open.spotify.com/show/1pCNZEjLmwKmSuxt8Bks6L
iTunes	https://podcasts.apple.com/us/podcast/smashhits-podcast/id1546728595

Table 5: Professional Networks

Professional networks	Link
ResearchGate	https://www.researchgate.net/project/smashHit-Smart-Dispatcher-for-Secure-and-Controlled-Sharing-of-Distributed-Personal-and-Industrial-Data
Mendeley	https://www.mendeley.com/profiles/smashhit-horizon-/
smashHit Website	www.smashhit.eu

3.3 smashHit Logo

The project's logo (see Figure 5) is in use in the branding of the smashHit project (e.g. in the deliverable templates and on the social media accounts).

Figure 5: smashHit Logo

AIM: To create a recognizable brand for the project, promote brand recognition and develop curiosity among relevant stakeholders.

We believe that additional project “branding” can be driven partially by the initial design of the website. i.e. images, style-guides. Other design elements, colour pallet etc. contribute to the outlook of the smashHit blog.

3.4 smashHit Website

One of the main sources of news for our audiences is the official smashHit website. It contains a description about the project, contact information of each partner, updates on the project, achievements, publications and events in which partners participated. The website is updated systematically and acts as the submission platform for the future stakeholder engagement.

AIM: To act as a central information resource for stakeholders, the research community and people who are interested in the project.

The domain name: <https://www.smashhit.eu/> has been reserved and is used for the smashHit project.

The website has a structure allowing us to present the project outcomes such as deliverables and scientific publications, news, basic information about the project (as depicted in Figure 6).

Figure 6: smashHit Website

3.5 Social Media Channels of smashHit

Social Media Platforms such as Twitter⁵² and LinkedIn⁵³ are the main tools for publicly presenting our results and keeping users informed with the progress of the smashHit project.

- **LinkedIn⁵³**
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/smashhit> (see also the image of the project profile on Figure 7)
During the duration of the project partners have been asked to provide the input about their progress and achievements together with a short description. Further, in order to reach wider audience and raise awareness, we repost relevant articles shared by others in our community thus assuring that the smashHit project stays active on the web.

⁵² <https://twitter.com>

⁵³ <https://www.linkedin.com>

Figure 7: smashHit LinkedIn Page

We stay active on LinkedIn by:

- having each partner regularly provide input for the posts, and re-posting these posts,
- engaging with others in the community and
- reposting relevant finding such as articles, events, news, software, videos.

- **Twitter**⁵²

<https://twitter.com/SmashhitP> (see also the image of the project profile on Figure 8)

In comparison to LinkedIn, which is aimed at professionals, Twitter provides a more diverse audience of people, which could be used as an advantage. Further, it is a dynamic platform and a source of news for many. Being present on Twitter would give the possibility to widely popularize smashHit among people from different backgrounds by reaching out to a wider more diverse audience. We use Twitter to:

- Post information about the project such as our mission and main goal.
- Engage with the research community by participating in conversations and adding comments.
- Attract possible collaborations.
- Raise awareness about smashHit.

With Twitter, we aim at presenting news, project results and keep the users updated about the progress of the project with the help of visual aids such as podcasts, video, images, tables and graphs. Further, call-to-action and hashtags are used to engage the users.

Further, we have extended our media presence for channels supporting the format of podcast, namely, **YouTube** (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnKnDSPB6fmn6kzKo716baA>),

Spotify (<https://open.spotify.com/show/1pCNZEjLmwKmSuxt8Bks6L>) and

iTunes (<https://podcasts.apple.com/us/podcast/smashhits-podcast/id1546728595>). Three dedicated podcasts containing interviews with project partners have been produced and distributed.

We use podcasts to:

- Explain what the project is working on in more detail.

- Communicate ongoing project work in an audio format, with the contents suitable for general audience and specialists interested in the topic.

Figure 9 is demonstrating the published podcasts and one of these channels, namely, Spotify.

Figure 8: smashHit Twitter Page

Figure 9: smashHit Spotify Page

3.6 Traditional Media and Newspapers

Some examples of traditional media and newspapers that the smashHit consortium partners envision to contact for dissemination of the project are (some of these traditional media also have an online presence and the dissemination would be performed via the print and/or online channels - given the COVID-19 developments even more emphasis is being put on online channels):

International Newspapers:

- Scitech Europa⁵⁴
- The European⁵⁵
- Pc Welt⁵⁶
- Traffic Technology Today⁵⁷
- Weserkurier⁵⁸
- Wired⁵⁹
- Business Insider⁶⁰
- TechCrunch⁶¹

Local Media and Newspapers:

- Tiroler Tageszeitung⁶²
- Austria Innovative⁶³
- Computer Bild⁶⁴
- IT Now⁶⁵
- TreeGic Magazine⁶⁶
- Weser Kurier⁶⁷

AIM: To popularize and promote this project's results and innovations by reaching out to different audiences.

⁵⁴ <https://www.scitecheuropa.eu>

⁵⁵ <https://the-european.eu>

⁵⁶ <https://www.pcwelt.de>

⁵⁷ <https://www.traffictotechnologytoday.com>

⁵⁸ <https://www.weser-kurier.de>

⁵⁹ <https://www.wired.com>

⁶⁰ <https://www.businessinsider.com>

⁶¹ <https://techcrunch.com>

⁶² <https://www.tt.com>

⁶³ <https://www.austriainnovativ.at>

⁶⁴ <http://computerbild.de>

⁶⁵ <https://www.bcs.org/membership/become-a-member/itnow/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.magzter.com/MX/TreeGic-Magazine/TreeGic-Magazine/Technology/>

⁶⁷ <https://www.weser-kurier.de/bremen.html>

LexisNexis Risk Solutions have a comprehensive database of all major European countries technical and trade press, plus contact methodologies for PR distribution and access to industry databases (some 1,200 publications) that LexisNexis Risk Solutions is willing to share with the consortium.

3.7 Blog Posts

A Blog containing the latest information about the project is being developed with specializing tools such as MailChimp⁶⁸ and Blogger⁶⁹ and updated regularly. The blog posts would deliver its message in a clear and attractive manner. At least 4 blog posts will be created. We believe that printed media is not within the main spirit of this project, nor it is efficient and easy to manage, thus most of the communication would be digital.

AIM: Create a network of interested parties around the project, which would help share results, publicise calls and raise awareness.

The blog posts have been published persistently. The initial plan for the blog posts is presented in Table 6; also, in this table, we have marked up the current status of the execution progress in this plan (where the fields marked up in green are the completed items) We have outperformed the initial plan by producing three introductory blog posts, three blog posts about own podcasts, and two calls for participation in surveys (conducted at the end of 2020, facilitating the data collection for the deliverables of other workpackages, see: <https://smashhit.eu/newsroom/>).

Table 6: smashHit Blog Post Planning and Execution

Blog Post	Release Date	Title	Topics	Created By
1	September 2020	The smashHit Project: general information, objectives and partners.	Purpose, Strategy, Aims and Objectives.	All
2	May 2021	The smashHit Business Cases 1 and 2: specifications, details and prototype	CPP and Insurance Data Integration, Traffic, Smart City and CPP Data Integration.	VW, LN, FVH
3	January 2022	Data Use Traceability and Fingerprinting	Traceability and Fingerprinting Approaches, Data Privacy.	LUH
4	September 2022	Automatic Contracting Tool and Consent Solution	smashHit Dispatcher, Semantic Models, Contract Building Blocks, Consent Management Solution	UIBK

3.8 Dissemination in EU technology platforms, co-operations with EU projects

The smashHit project communicates and disseminates to other EU technology platforms and projects, as well as thematic platforms (e.g. smart city platforms).

Cooperation with the following platforms is aimed at and/or already carried out:

⁶⁸ <https://mailchimp.com>

⁶⁹ <https://www.blogger.com>

- **BDVA⁷⁰**: our solution for data driven digital transformations could contribute to the policy development and technology ramification supported by the BDVA.
- **NESSI⁷¹**: smashHit will include software development and platforms such as NESSI could provide valuable inputs about research and technology matters related to the software domain.

The cooperation with other (on-going) EU projects is carried out as follows:

- **CampaNeo**: the semantic consent models are being developed in coordination between the two projects, also cooperation in the data management area and use case level will be sought.
- **DALICC²³**: smashHit is employing the project's outcomes in the area of semantic content and data licensing [3], and also collaborates with the other follow up activities of the DALICC project.
- **Cross-CPP**: since ATB is the coordinator of Cross-CPP having other partners in common (TOG, ATOS and VW), and Cross-CPP that is dealing with CPP data offered in a Marketplace to be used in cross-sectorial services, the topic is quite relevant for the smashHit project and thus many contact points are made between the projects.
- **I3-MARKET⁷²**: this project addresses the growing demand for a single European Data Market Economy by innovating marketplace platforms, demonstrating with industrial implementations that the data economy growth is possible. The i3-MARKET proposal provides technologies for trustworthy (secure and reliable) data-driven collaboration and federation of existing and new future marketplace platforms. Special attention is on industrial data and particularly on sensitive commercial data assets from both SMEs to large industrial corporations. ATOS is part of these 14 consortium partners by providing the AGORA solution as a pilot for the automotive sector. Therefore, the synergies and collaboration between I3-MARKET and smashHit could leverage networking opportunities and knowledge exchange between both projects.
- **TRUSTS (Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space)**: the project builds on two large national data market projects and wants to allow the integration of multiple platform, which work under different jurisdictions. The developed data-sharing platform aims to be the basis for secure, trustworthy and GDPR-compliant data exchanges. The focus of this project is on the integration and interoperability of different (national) data markets. L3S is the lead and coordinator of the consortium consisting of 17 partners. L3S is exchanging information between the smashHit and the TRUSTS project to identify synergies and maximise both project impacts.
- **DataVaults⁷³**: the project aims to address issues such as data privacy, ethics and intellectual property rights by allowing users to be in control of their data and with who it is shared. The DataVaults framework and platform focuses on personal data and its representation as a multidimensional ecosystem that is regulated by smart contracts. Both DataVaults and smashHit are closely related when it comes to the topics of data protection and user rights. As being a part of the 17 partners involved in the DataVaults project, ATOS could help establish future collaboration with smashHit, which could be mutually beneficial.

3.9 Events, Conferences and Journals

Participation in talks, panel discussions, conferences and workshops is essential for the dissemination of the smashHit project. Further, smashHit also aims at publishing in various journals:

- Publishing in **open access journals**, which would make the data and content available immediately.
- **Publishing via the "gold" route**, whereby authors pay a fee to publish material as open access immediately. This is usually offered by most of the high-level journals and would be seen as a potential direct cost in the smashHit budget.

⁷⁰ <http://www.bdva.eu>

⁷¹ <http://www.nessi-europe.com/default.aspx?page=home>

⁷² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871754/es>

⁷³ <https://www.datavaults.eu>

- **Publishing via the “green” route.** Materials would be stored in a disciplinary, institutional or public repository (Section 3.1) and would be available as open access after a specific embargo period.

AIM: To publicise the project and share results with the research communities and encourage involvement which could lead to future collaborations. Further, create a multi-disciplinary innovation community to contribute to the project.

A detailed and complete overview of events at which smashHit was presented by consortium members is provided in the data appendix file for this deliverable [5]. The attended events with the project presentation so far are as follows.

Events where partners participated in 2020:

- BDV PPP Summit (ATOS)
- EBDVF 2020 (ATOS)
- BDV PPP GOING VIRTUAL – DATA PLATFORM WEBINARS (ATB)
- Big Data PPP Mixed Data Platforms: “B2B and B2C together” (ATB)
- Using the Connected Car’s Digital Data in the Real World (ATB, LNRS)
- Internal meeting (UIBK)
- NODES 2020 Neo4j Online Developer Expo and Summit (UIBK)
- SEMIC Conference 2020 (LUH, UBO)
- Profiles workshop (LUH, UBO)
- Symposium Intelligente Mobilität (LUH)
- Internal meeting – 2 times (VW)
- BDVA Standards Workshop (TOG)
- Making Data Useful Conference (TOG)
- H2020 Project Information Exchange (TOG, VW, ATB)
- Automotive Edge Hackathon (VW)
- Hackathon presentation (VW)

Events where partners participated in 2021:

- Big Data and Security (BDS) Internal Innovation workshop (ATOS)
- BDVA/DAIRO Activity Group meeting 43, 18th - 19th of March, SESSION 2: Two-sided/Multi-sided aspects of data platforms (ATB)
- Colloquium on data science and artificial intelligence (UIBK)
- GISRUK Online Seminar Series 2021 (UBO, LUH)
- 2021 Oil and Gas High Performance Computing Conference (UIBK)
- Data Week 2021 Workshop (ATB)
- Open Digital Standards Conference (TOG)
- Internal meeting – 3 times (VW)
- European Semantic Web Conference – 2 presentations (UIBK)

For further potential events and publication venues where the project may participate, see Section 3.9 of the project’s D8.1 [1].

The communication and dissemination mention all the project’s partners in the communication and dissemination connections whenever possible, as it gives visibility to partner organizations and enhances long term impact beyond the EU-project lifetime. Naturally, the project also follows the Horizon 2020 Communication guidelines⁷⁴, and will be explicitly acknowledging the EU funding in the communication⁷⁵.

3.10 Final Exhibition

In order to display and present the results of smashHit, a final project event is planned to be organized. It is to include European policy makers, high-profile association representatives, major research institutions, major industry bodies and intermediaries, regulatory bodies at national and European levels.

⁷⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/acknowledge-funding_en.htm

⁷⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

According to the smashHit proposal, the final exhibition needs to have at least 100 high level participants.

LN indicated that there is a possibility of organizing a smashHit-focused event towards the end of 2022. The event could be held in Munich, Wolfsburg, or Helsinki due to automotive manufacturers and the project's Smart City use case. The project and its results will be presented to the attending insurance and automobile companies in order to raise awareness and share innovations. If the COVID-19 pandemic persists, the event may be held online and the plan may need to be revised.

AIM: To ensure that potential stakeholders are aware of the smashHit project's contributions and to demonstrate their value. Most of all, to publicise the project's results and recommendations to further support the data value chain.

3.11 Communication Material

Further, the project has the project flyer and poster template. These can be and are shared online through the smashHit social media channels, and on workshops and conferences.

Figure 10 presents the design of the smashHit poster, this version is editable and is being adjusted according to the needs.

AIM: To act as a central information resource for stakeholders interested in the project and to present the smashHit project and its purpose.

A SMART DISPATCHER FOR THE SECURED & CONTROLLED EXCHANGE OF PERSONAL AND INDUSTRIAL DATA

OVERALL OBJECTIVE: TO GUARANTEE TRACEABILITY, TRUST, SECURITY AND PRIVACY EXAMPLES

To enable the secure exchange of personal and industrial data right across industries

The creation of a smart dispatcher system to obtain approval and compliance with legal requirements such as GDPR for efficiently regulated contracts

The development of a secure data protection mechanism including traceability

SEMANTIC CONSENT & CONTRACTS:

- The management of consent of data usage in cases such as changing drivers or selling of cars
- Semantic models for understandable, automated contracts make it easier to understand and to create new business models

TRACEABLE DATA USAGE:

- Digital watermark / fingerprint
- Checking the data offered illegally for authenticity and information about the parties involved
- Identification of the trigger of a data leak for the faster resolution of security weak points

BUSINESS CASES

INTELLIGENT USE OF VEHICLE DATA

- New insurance models, such as mileage-based vehicle insurance
- Benefit from safe driving behavior without the need for any additional hardware
- Control of transmitted data

SMART CITY HELSINKI

- Receive real time route recommendations in-vehicle
- Timely information on traffic jams
- Sensor data, such as temperature or air quality

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Figure 10: smashHit Poster / Handout

4 Dissemination and Communication Reporting

The dissemination and communication continue to develop though the whole span of the smashHit project. All partners contribute to the dissemination by sharing their progress on social media, attend events, publish in journals, and appear in media and local newspapers. A reporting template with specific metrics is used for monitoring partners' contributions through the whole project's timeline, specifically, summarising events and publications. For the first half of the project, the filled out report from all partners is available as Excel file, containing all the details [5].

4.1 Success Metrics

Here, we define the targeted key performance metrics for our different dissemination activities, and analyse how they are met so far. Each table below specifies what KPIs are expected to be met with regards to the corresponding activities. The provided values would be used as a guideline when evaluating the progress of the project and could fluctuate.

The KPI's are combined across the full consortium and assuming a 36-month duration. Our existing insights and web resources attain these numbers. We use IP tracking so we can see at an organisational / company level – metrics that may be better to look at. For example, which and how many visitors we cover rather than how many sessions we observe, etc.

Dissemination of the project includes participation in various events, newsletters, scientific publications, etc. An overview of all desired KPIs are described in Table 7. Tables 8-12 provide more detailed success metrics that are activity based.

Table 7: Overall Dissemination and Communication smashHit KPIs

Activity	Success Rate
Use case and technology project open sessions	KPI: More than 50 ecosystem members attending.
Participation in workshops, conferences and other international events	KPI: More than 10 events.
Briefings and demonstrations at third-party events	KPI: Attend more than 20 such events where the number of stakeholders is more than 1000.
Newsletters	KPI: At least 4.
Scientific publications	KPI: 3-5 and technical contributions.
Final Exhibition	KPI: >100 high-level participants in the final event.

The project's website is one of the main tools for popularization of the smashHit project and provides the latest news and discoveries. It may be the core platform for information, but we use social media, press releases, conferences etc. to drive traffic to it. Desired KPIs are presented in Table 8; we also highlight with colour where we currently are in terms of achievement of these KPIs.

Number of sessions represents a group of user interactions with our website that takes place within a given time frame.

Number of page views identifies the number of individual users who visited the website.

Number of unique views is the number of the unique users that click on a tracking link of a campaign⁷⁶.

Number of followers measures the number of users who decided to follow smashHit on social media.

⁷⁶ <https://www.similarweb.com/corp/blog/unique-visitors/>

Table 8: Website Metrics

Project's Website (2020-2022)	Poor	Good	Excellent
Number of sessions	<2,000	2,000-7,000	7,000+
Number of page views	<10,000	10,000-15,000	15,000+
Number of unique visitors	<3,000	3,000-7,000	7,000+

The actual figures of the performance of the smashHit website are presented in Figure 11: smashHit Website Performance (Status: June 9, 2021) Figure 11. Note that the Google Analytics traffic tracker has been set on the website only in May 2020, so the actual figures are slightly larger. As one can see, the website is being accessed regularly and globally, as expected.

Demographics	Country	Users	% Users
Language	1. United States	326	16.11%
Country	2. Germany	189	9.34%
City	3. Finland	105	5.19%
System	4. Austria	103	5.09%
Browser	5. Spain	85	4.20%
Operating System	6. United Kingdom	84	4.15%
Service Provider	7. China	80	3.95%
Mobile	8. India	62	3.06%
Operating System	9. Netherlands	58	2.87%

Figure 11: smashHit Website Performance (Status: June 9, 2021)

Social Media such as Twitter and LinkedIn would need to meet the following metrics (Table 9). Here, we also highlight with colour where we currently are in terms of achievement of these KPIs. The specified metrics are for the whole duration of the project. Successful presence on Twitter and LinkedIn will be measured by keeping track of the new followers, likes and post. Each partner would contribute to this by posting and resharing featured posts.

Table 9: Social Media Metrics

Social Media	Poor	Good	Excellent
Twitter followers	<500	500-800	800+
Twitter posts	<100	100-200	200+
Twitter likes	<300	300-600	600+
Twitter post shares	<100	100-200	200+
LinkedIn followers	<150	150-250	250+
LinkedIn posts	<100	100-200	200+
LinkedIn likes	<300	300-600	600+
LinkedIn post shares	<100	100-200	200+

In June 2021, at the time of the writing of the deliverable, the key figures for the key social media channels have been as follows:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/smashhitP>

- currently **117 followers, 411 posts**
- **LinkedIn:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/smashhit>
- currently **115 followers, regular posts** – see the LinkedIn public profile

Figure 12: smashHit – LinkedIn Impressions for June 2020-June 2021 (status: June 30, 2021)

For podcasts, the consumption/downloads of the produced content in total (on YouTube, Spotify, iTunes) have been amounting to 188 times.

As visible from the Excel sheet with the involvement with events and statistics from online media, the project is already predominantly in the “Good” and sometimes in the “Excellent” range w.r.t. the targeted KPIs. In all following tables, we highlight with a background color the thresholds that have been already achieved as of now.

Specific metrics about media presence for the whole duration of the project are defined in Table 10; while in Table 11 we define KPIs for attending conferences (EU and International) and events (public events, workshops, conferences) during the lifespan of the project.

Table 10: Media Communication and Newsletters Metrics

Media Communication and Newsletters	Poor	Good	Excellent
Number of media articles mentioning smashHit	<10	10-20	20+
Number of newsletters circulated	<4	4-8	8+

This numbers presented in Table 11 are valid for the situation at the moment of initial planning. Taking into account the COVID-19 some of these events would be organised online thus KPI metrics could be different.

The key newsletters appearances are as follows (detailed and further information is in the data appendix [5]).

Key newsletters and media appearances by the partners in 2020:

- ATOS Research and Innovation (ARI) Newsletter (ATOS)
- Kysely henkilötietojen hyödyntämisestä (FVH)
- Consumer content & data security survey (FVH)
- Secure data sharing: the SmashHit project (FVH)
- Survey for data consumers and Survey for Data Providers (ATOS, UIBK as smashHit project newsletter)

Key newsletters and media appearances by the partners in 2021:

- Enabling Interpretability in Smart Cities With Knowledge Graphs: Towards a Better Modelling of Consent (UIBK at IEEE Smart Cities eNewsletter)
- SmashHit-hankkeelta Innovaatiokonsepti (FVH)

Additionally, the partners have been delivering dedicated webpages, blog and social media posts on various channels [5].

Table 11: Conference and Events Metrics

Conference and Events	Poor	Good	Excellent
Number of conferences and workshops where smashHit is presented	<10	10-20	20+
Number of third-party events with audience >1000	<20	20-30	30+

Naturally due to pandemics, participation in very large physical events is hindered, but is partly replaced by events with online participation and increased presence on social media platforms.

Publications in journals will help popularize the project and share our achievements with the academia and public. KPIs are shown in Table 12.

Table 12: Publications Metrics

Publications	Poor	Good	Excellent
Number of published papers	<5	5-10	10+

As visible from the Excel sheet associated with this deliverable [5] and the tables of this section, the project is already in the “Good” range w.r.t. the publication metrics. The accepted academic publications are at high profile competitive venues, such as in *Semantic Web* journal, European Semantic Web Conference, International Journal of Geo-Information. The up to date scientific publications stemming from the project are as follows:

- Kurteva A., Chhetri T.R., Pandit H.J., Fensel A. (2021). "Consent through the lens of semantics: state of the art survey and best practices". *Semantic Web – Interoperability, Usability, Applicability - an IOS Press Journal*, in press.
- Tempelmeier N., Feuerhake U., Wage O., Demidova E. "Mining Topological Dependencies of Recurrent Congestion in Road Networks". *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*. 2021; 10(4):248.

- Bless C., Dötlinger L., Kaltschmid M., Reiter M., Kurteva A., Roa-Valverde A.J, Fensel, A. (2021). "Raising Awareness of Data Sharing Consent Through Knowledge Graph Visualisation". In *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Semantic Systems (SEMANTICS 2021)*, IOS Press in Studies on the Semantic Web, in press.
- Chhetri T.R. (2021). "Improving Decision Making using Semantic Web Technologies". In *Proceedings of European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2021) PhD Symposium*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science 12739, Springer.
- Dadwal R., Funke T., Demidova E. (2021). „An Adaptive Clustering Approach for Accident Prediction". In *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation (ITSC2021)*, in press.
- Kurteva A. (2021). "Implementing Informed Consent with Knowledge Graphs". In *Proceedings of European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2021) PhD Symposium*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science 12739, Springer.
- Sao A., Tempelmeier N., Demidova E. (2021). "Deep Information Fusion for Electric Vehicle Charging Station Occupancy Forecasting". In *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation (ITSC2021)*, in press.

Further, one doctoral dissertation connected with the project has been defended:

- Thorben Funke (LUH): "Analyzing and Predicting Material Flow Networks Using Stochastic Block Models and Statistical Graph Embeddings", 2020.

4.2 Possible Changes in the Plan due to COVID-19

All partners in the smashHit project acknowledged the COVID-19 virus circumstances and their likely implications on the communication and dissemination of the project. smashHit follows its communication and dissemination activities as planned, with the needed adjustments (more of online than offline communication, in particular).

The current conditions do not allow face-to-face meetings, thus some of the planned briefings and presentations carried out by the smashHit's partners will be done online instead. This is achieved with the help of online communication tools such as WebEx⁷⁷, Zoom⁷⁸ or Skype⁷⁹. Presentations at large industrial events may become possible again at a later point of time in the project, and in this case, they will be made then. When it comes to the research and educational activities of the project, the production of research papers and teaching has been affected less, as submissions to scientific journals and conferences are typically done online, and the same holds meanwhile for teaching. Further, most of the scientific conferences have gone into the online mode or get postponed. To cover the possible gaps in the dissemination and communication, all partners aimed at engaging more in alternative channels e.g. establishing a stronger social media presence on Twitter, LinkedIn and on the smashHit's personal and partner's websites in order to continue the communication and dissemination of the project. Additional efforts have been placed into production of further, additional to the initial plan material, such as podcasts, and presence at the corresponding relevant platforms (such as YouTube, Spotify, iTunes) and dissemination there. Depending on the state of the pandemic situation, future events and activities will be discussed and changes in this plan will be made accordingly to ensure the activity level similar to the planned one.

⁷⁷ <https://www.webex.com>

⁷⁸ <https://zoom.us>

⁷⁹ <https://www.skype.com/bg/>

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, we presented the dissemination and communication report for the first half of the smashHit Horizon 2020 EU project. The communication and dissemination strategy helps the project's popularization among all stakeholders, including a wider audience. Participating in various events, conferences and workshops enhances the smashHit presence among the scientific community and helps to find possible future collaborations. Establishing a strong social media presence is beneficial and a good opportunity to raise awareness about topics such as Mobility, Semantic Technology, Data Privacy and Security, and more. It introduces our innovations to the public and build a wide network for knowledge exchange and collaboration.

To conclude, the dissemination and communication are running on track, with some adjustments in the planning (especially due to the COVID-19 pandemics), and they will continue through the whole project and involve all partners' contributions about activities and feedback on their progress. Collaboration, communication and the broader networks between all project partners is essential for the successful dissemination of the smashHit project and will help build good work ethics, communication skills and recommendation practise for future projects.

6 References

- [1] smashHit consortium, „D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan,“ March 2020.
- [2] A. Remke, “enviroCar: A Citizen Science Platform for Analyzing and Mapping Crowd-Sourced Car Sensor Data”, [Online]. Available at: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/b76b/6f89d4169a56444b85fd5ddea0e68787b945.pdf>. [Accessed 22 12 2019].
- [3] E. Kanjo, S. Benford, M. Paxton, A. Chamberlain, D. Fraser, D. Woodgate, D. Crellin, A. Woolard, “Mob-GeoSen: facilitating personal geosensor data collection and visualization using mobile phones”, Springer-Verlag, 2007.
- [4] T. Pellegrini, V. Mireles, S. Steyskal, O. Panasiuk, A. Fensel, & S. Kirrane, "[Automated Rights Clearance Using Semantic Web Technologies: The DALICC Framework](#)", Semantic Applications (pp. 203-218), Springer Vieweg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2018.
- [5] Detailed list of smashHit events and publications, Excel sheet, [Online]. Available as a dataset associated with this deliverable at: <https://smashhit.eu/deliverables>

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